

Efficient inference of quantum system parameters by approximate Bayesian computation

Lewis A. Clark^{1,2,*} and Jan Kołodzyński^{2,3,†}

¹*Department of Optics, Palacky University, 17. listopadu 1192/12, 77146 Olomouc, Czechia*

²*Centre for Quantum Optical Technologies, Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Banacha 2c, 02-097 Warsaw, Poland*

³*Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Aleja Lotników 32/46, 02-668 Warsaw, Poland*

 (Received 25 July 2024; revised 22 February 2025; accepted 18 March 2025; published 18 April 2025)

The ability to efficiently infer system parameters is essential in any signal-processing task that requires fast operation. In quantum systems, a serious challenge arises due to substantial growth of the underlying Hilbert space with the system size. As the statistics of the measurement data observed—i.e., the *likelihood*—can no longer be easily computed, common approaches such as maximum-likelihood estimators or particle filters become impractical. To address this issue, we propose the use of the approximate Bayesian computation (ABC) algorithm, which evades likelihood computation by sampling from a library of measurement data—*a priori* prepared for a given quantum device. We apply ABC to interpret photodetection click patterns arising from real-time probing of a two-level atom and an optomechanical system. For the latter, we consider both linear and nonlinear regimes to show how to tailor the ABC algorithm by understanding the quantum measurement statistics. Our work demonstrates that fast parameter inference may be possible regardless of the complexity of the quantum device and the measurement scheme involved.

DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevApplied.23.044040](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.23.044040)

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum statistical inference [1] forms an essential part of any sensing scenario in which a quantum system is used to probe external parameters affecting its dynamics [2–5]. It lies at the core of quantum metrology protocols [6–8], which can offer unprecedented sensitivity thanks to genuine quantum effects, e.g., entanglement [9] or others [10], exhibited by the sensor. This has led to breakthroughs in the construction of ultraprecise clocks [11], magnetometers [12], interferometers [13,14], or even gravitational-wave detectors [15]. The latter, in fact, serves as a seminal example in which signal extraction of cosmic events may only be possible by using state-of-the-art sampling-based inference techniques [16,17].

Furthermore, the gravitational-wave detector [18] can be viewed as an optomechanical device [19] operating in a two-stage transducing architecture, in which an external signal (gravitational wave) affects a well-isolated quantum

sensor (mirrors) that is continuously measured (optically) in real time [20,21]. The same picture applies to atomic sensors [12], where it is the atomic spin that is sensitive to external magnetic fields while being simultaneously monitored by light [22–25]. The formalism of continuous quantum measurements [26–28] allows one to build a model describing both the detection process and (conditional) sensor dynamics. Based on this, statistical inference can be used to interpret the measured data and extract the signal being sensed [29–31]. Moreover, if this can be done *efficiently*, i.e., quickly, the information may be used “on the fly” to further enhance the process by controlling the device in real time and applying active feedback [32–34]. This has been spectacularly demonstrated in optomechanical devices [35–38] and also in systems involving levitated nanoparticles [39,40], when probed by optical homodyning [31]. In such cases, as the Gaussianity of the overall dynamical and measurement processes can be assured, statistical inference can indeed be performed quickly, e.g., via Kalman filtering [20,41,42].

In contrast, the use of *photon-counting measurements* poses a serious challenge from the perspective of statistical inference [30], which, if overcome, could lead to various breakthroughs, particularly as photodetection has recently been adopted for probing optomechanical devices [43–46]. In Fig. 1(a), we present a scheme in which a general quantum system is probed by light that subsequently undergoes

*Contact author: drlewisalark@gmail.com

†Contact author: jankolo@ifpan.edu.pl

Published by the American Physical Society under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. Further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the published article's title, journal citation, and DOI.

FIG. 1. Parameter inference in the quantum setting. (a) A parameter θ is encoded onto a quantum system during its evolution. To infer the parameter value, the system is probed by an external field (red arrow), e.g., light, that is subsequently measured (black arrow). In parallel, the system experiences dissipation and excitation due to interactions with a bath. As long as the impact of the bath on the system is memoryless (Markovian), it can always be modeled as interactions with virtual external fields whose measurements are, however, *inaccessible*. (b) The value of θ is inferred from the *accessible* data D —here, a pattern of photon clicks observed at distinct times—by reconstructing the *posterior distribution* $p(\theta|D)$. This requires explicitly determining the form of the *likelihood* $p(D|\theta)$ for any θ , given the specific dynamics of the system. Such a “full computation” can be avoided by resorting to the *approximate Bayesian computation* (ABC) algorithm, which allows for an approximate reconstruction of the posterior, $p^*(\theta|D)$, by sampling from a library of detection patterns generated in advance for different values of θ .

photodetection. Some external or internal parameter, θ , is encoded onto the system during the probing time, while the system also dissipates due to inevitable interactions with its environment. The goal is to infer information about θ from a photon-click pattern, D , recorded by detecting emitted photons in real time within some *accessible* channel.

An important tool allowing one to ease the simulation of system dynamics is quantum Monte Carlo methods [47–51]. These methods allow any (Markovian) bath-induced dissipation to be unraveled, i.e., interpreted as a virtual quantum-jump process yielding emissions into or excitations from fictitious *inaccessible* channels, as shown in Fig. 1(a). Although one must (ensemble) average over the trajectories of such “unobservable jumps” to obtain the true system dynamics, recording a single trajectory suffices if one is interested solely in generating a click pattern of the observed photons, D , while ignoring “unobservable clicks.”

Now, as shown in Fig. 1(b), the purpose of Bayesian statistical inference is to reconstruct the posterior distribution $p(\theta|D)$ [52,53] that most accurately represents our knowledge about θ given a particular detected photon-click pattern D . Even when performed numerically, this requires both sampling from the *likelihood* $p(D|\theta)$ for different values of θ and assuming that $p(D|\theta)$ can be computed quickly. The first issue constitutes the main bottleneck in common inference problems where the θ -parameter space is vast. To mitigate this, various methods, such as particle filters [54,55] or Markov-chain Monte Carlo samplers [55,56] (e.g., the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm [29]), have been developed to relax the problem and consider only statistically relevant values of θ ; however, within the quantum setting, in which the dimension of the density matrix scales significantly with system size, computing the likelihood itself often poses a serious challenge. As shown in Fig. 1(b), this typically requires simulations of the system dynamics along a particular trajectory D being observed. Unless the underlying system can be treated as an ensemble of independent constituents of moderate dimension, e.g., atoms in atomic clocks [57], or obeys some symmetry allowing the effective size of its wavefunction to be reduced [58,59], the likelihood computation becomes impractical. This is especially true for long trajectories, where integration time increases, let alone when aiming for the speeds necessary to implement active inference-based feedback operations [35–40].

In our work, we demonstrate that the above challenge can be overcome by resorting to so-called *likelihood-free inference methods*, namely ABC [60–62], which has previously been applied in the quantum context of Markov processes [63] and Hamiltonian learning [64,65]. In particular, as schematically depicted in Fig. 1(b), rather than trying to explicitly reconstruct the posterior $p(\theta|D)$ based on the system dynamical model, one stores *a priori* a sufficiently large library of detection click patterns generated for different values of θ . Upon observing D , the posterior can then be reconstructed by *rejection sampling*, i.e., by randomly drawing datasets of known parameter θ from the library and testing them against D based on either key statistical properties (*summary statistics*) that must be appropriately chosen [62] or by directly comparing them against D with a suitable distance measure, which introduces some additional but modest computational cost [66]. Despite being approximate, ABC allows one, in principle, to control the error in reconstructing $p(\theta|D)$ [62], in contrast methods based on machine learning [67–72], which are fast once trained but heuristic [54]. Although in parameter-estimation tasks it is often sufficient to infer only relevant features of the posterior [53], e.g., dominant moments of the distribution, let us emphasize that our priority here is to verify ABC itself and assess its accuracy in reconstructing the full posterior. More precisely, we shall

quantify how well the posterior produced by ABC represents its true form, rather than compare its parameter estimation capabilities.

To study the capabilities of the ABC algorithm in quantum parameter inference (posterior reconstruction), we consider three different scenarios: a two-level atom, a linear optomechanical system, and a nonlinear optomechanical system, in all of which we consider continuous semiclassical driving and the parameter to be inferred is the detuning of the laser driving from the device. For the two-level atom, the posterior distribution can be derived analytically, meaning there is no benefit to using ABC. Nevertheless, it serves as a useful benchmark for demonstrating the effectiveness of the algorithm and the simplicity of its construction. For the linear optomechanical system, only approximate analytic solutions can be obtained, so numerical methods are required to obtain the true posterior. Hence, the ABC algorithm starts to be useful, although model-based brute-force posterior reconstruction remains computationally feasible. In stark contrast, operating the optomechanical system in the nonlinear regime, the computation cost of exhaustive methods becomes prohibitive, making the ABC algorithm essential for reconstructing the posterior distribution within a reasonable times; however, for ABC to be effective in this setting, a thorough understanding of the quantum statistics underlying the measurement data is crucial.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Sec. II, we summarize the key concepts of Bayesian inference before presenting the ABC algorithm and its application. In Sec. III, we then demonstrate how to unravel the dissipative dynamics of an open quantum system into respective trajectories while being monitored via photon counting. Next, in Sec. IV, we introduce the physical models we consider—a two-level atom, as well as linear and nonlinear optomechanical systems—and apply the theory of Sec. III to these cases. Finally, in Sec. V, we study the problem of parameter inference for the three scenarios and, in particular, the performance of the ABC algorithm. We conclude our work in Sec. VI.

II. BAYESIAN INFERENCE WITHOUT LIKELIHOOD COMPUTATION

In this section, we review the fundamentals of Bayesian inference, highlighting the challenges encountered when applying it. We begin by recalling the definition of the Bayesian posterior distribution given some measurement data, and then describe how the ABC algorithm operates to reconstruct this approximately, but sufficiently, without the need for explicit computation.

A. Bayesian inference

As sketched in Fig. 1(b), the purpose of Bayesian inference is to reconstruct the distribution describing our

knowledge about a parameter θ after gathering the measured data D . Formally, within Bayesian inference, the unknown parameter is treated as a random variable, and its likelihood is calculated over a range of parameter values. Our initial knowledge about the parameter is included in the form of a prior distribution. The essential form of Bayesian inference is then given by Bayes's rule [53]:

$$p(\theta|D) = \frac{p(D|\theta)p(\theta)}{p(D)} = \frac{p(D|\theta)p(\theta)}{\int d\theta p(D|\theta)p(\theta)}, \quad (1)$$

which defines the posterior distribution $p(\theta|D)$ based on the likelihood $p(D|\theta)$ and the prior distribution $p(\theta)$.

Importantly, for a given model and measurement process, the likelihood is in principle determinable; however, it may be hard to evaluate in practice. Nonetheless, much research in classical estimation theory and statistics has focused on avoiding the computation of the denominator in Eq. (1) [54]. This is because the parameter space of θ can be extremely large and multidimensional, making the integral over the entire space a typical bottleneck in the computation.

1. Reconstructing the posterior by sampling

To mitigate the problem of computing the denominator in Eq. (1), sampling methods can be used. The most basic of these is known as *rejection sampling* [54]. Suppose we do not have access to the full posterior $p(\theta|D)$ but are able to efficiently compute some unnormalized version of it, e.g., $\tilde{p}(\theta|D) = p(D|\theta)p(\theta)$. While the posterior is automatically normalized with respect to D , normalizing correctly over the full range of θ can be computationally challenging without the use of sampling. This is particularly true for large or multidimensional parameter spaces. To conduct such sampling, we first choose a (typically simple) *proposal distribution* from which the samples of θ are drawn. A natural candidate for this in Bayesian inference is the prior $p(\theta)$. The method is guaranteed to work as long as we can find a constant M (preferably the smallest possible) such that the inequality $Mp(\theta) \geq \tilde{p}(\theta|D)$ is fulfilled for any value of θ . In other words, $Mp(\theta)$ provides a valid upper bound on the distribution $\tilde{p}(\theta|D)$, although it may only be tight for some particular values of θ .

The rejection sampling method proceeds as follows. We first draw a sample of θ from the proposal distribution, $p(\theta)$, and then we proceed to determine whether it should be accepted or rejected. To do this, we draw some value u from the uniform distribution $U(0, 1)$ and accept the sampled θ if the condition

$$u \leq \frac{\tilde{p}(\theta|D)}{Mp(\theta)} \quad (2)$$

is satisfied. As a result, the values of θ being accepted are actually drawn from the normalized version of $\tilde{p}(\theta|D)$, i.e.,

the true posterior. Hence, by sampling long enough, the full posterior $p(\theta|D)$ can be reconstructed.

The efficiency of this method is determined by the probability of acceptance

$$p(\text{accept}) = \int d\theta \frac{\tilde{p}(\theta|D)}{Mp(\theta)} p(\theta) = \frac{1}{M} \int d\theta \tilde{p}(\theta|D), \quad (3)$$

which is maximized by choosing the smallest possible M such that the constraint $Mp(\theta) \geq \tilde{p}(\theta|D)$ is fulfilled for any θ .

When the parameter space becomes large, rejection sampling can become inefficient, particularly if the proposal distribution (the prior) is not tight to the posterior. To improve the sampling efficiency, methodologies involving Monte Carlo approaches, such as Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithms and particle filters [54,55], have been developed. In this way, the need to search across the whole parameter space can be negated, as the algorithms are designed to focus on areas with higher likelihood.

Nevertheless, the tractability of the problem described here requires that at least the likelihood is simple to obtain; however, in many complex systems [60,63], such as when the likelihood needs to be computationally generated for a highly variable dataset, this is not the case. In particular, this applies in the quantum setting within which, unless some analytic shortcuts can be established, computing the likelihood requires full simulation of the dynamics given a particular quantum-jump pattern fixed by the measurement data recorded. In such cases, it is actually the determination of $p(D|\theta)$ that requires our attention. To circumvent this, we resort to a branch of statistics known as *likelihood-free inference* [62].

B. Approximate Bayesian computation

In this work, we focus on a particularly successful technique of likelihood-free inference, ABC [61,62]. Before going into the technical details of how the algorithm works, we first motivate the problem as follows. Suppose we are dealing with a system for which the likelihood of obtaining particular measurement data is difficult to compute, as it requires reproducing the (conditional) system dynamics; however, simulating instances of measurement data is relatively easy. In such a case, it should still be possible to efficiently perform inference by sampling, as described above, by using a precomputed storage of the measurement data.

In particular, suppose we have a precomputed library of datasets, each generated for a known value of θ . Then, ABC can be viewed as a variation of the rejection sampling method described above. Similarly, we start by sampling a value of θ from the proposal distribution, $p(\theta)$. Based on this, we choose a subset of the library (dataset pool) containing datasets generated with the sampled θ . We then draw a dataset D' from this subset and compare it against

the observed dataset D . If the datasets are equivalent, we accept the sampled value of θ , i.e.,

$$\text{Accept if: } D = D'. \quad (4)$$

With sufficient sampling, it is clear how this leads to the generation of the posterior. The chance of the dataset being equivalent to the one drawn is proportional to the likelihood of the distribution being generated with that particular value of the parameter. In the ideal case of each dataset pool (for each value of θ) containing all possible datasets, when sampling over the entire library, the probability of acceptance is exactly the likelihood, $p(D|\theta)$ [62]. Moreover, by letting the proposal distribution be the prior, $p(\theta)$, as in rejection sampling, θ is effectively drawn from a distribution proportional to the product of these two quantities, i.e., the posterior.

Clearly, though, this procedure is only theoretical, as the probability of the exact dataset existing in the library is negligibly small. We therefore need to relax the acceptance criteria to be able to obtain solution samples in reasonable times. This is done in the following two ways.

1. Summary statistics

Instead of comparing the datasets directly, we can instead compare them based on simpler statistics of the distribution. These could include the mean, median, or any moment of the data. These so-called *summary statistics* will generally be less informative than the full posterior of the data but can be efficiently computed for any given dataset D . Furthermore, the summary statistic is said to be *sufficient* for a given dataset D if the posterior distribution can be expressed as a function of the summary statistic rather than the data, as described in Refs. [61,73]:

$$p(\theta|D) = p(\theta|S(D)). \quad (5)$$

Although this may not always hold, a given summary statistic can still provide enough information to distinguish the datasets, allowing a reasonable approximation of the true posterior to be provided. Thus, comparing the summary statistics of the dataset to those drawn from the library should be enough if the summary statistics are either sufficient or at least close to being sufficient. The acceptance rule (4) is then relaxed to

$$\text{Accept if: } S(D) = S(D'), \quad (6)$$

where, for generality, we now let the function $S(\cdot)$ contain multiple statistics (e.g., higher and higher moments)—the more statistics are included, as long as they provide useful information to distinguish between datasets, the closer $S(D)$ is to satisfying the sufficiency condition (5).

2. Relaxation of acceptance criteria

Requiring that the datasets, or their summary statistics, match exactly is a strict criterion of acceptance that is unlikely to be fulfilled in most cases, especially for large and variable datasets. The sampling procedure is therefore still inefficient. To allow for computation in reasonable timescales, we thus relax the acceptance criteria such that we require only that the datasets are close to one another. More precisely, given some statistical distance δ , the acceptance rule (6) is further relaxed as follows:

$$\text{Accept if: } \delta(S(D), S(D')) \leq \epsilon, \quad (7)$$

where ϵ is a *threshold of acceptance* that we can choose according to our needs. For summary statistics with scalar outcomes, we can use the absolute difference as our distance, meaning we have

$$\text{Accept if: } |S(D) - S(D')| \leq \epsilon. \quad (8)$$

If multiple statistics are used, the acceptance rule can be defined individually for each, or as some combined statistical distance. Within this work, we shall use an individual rule for each summary statistic. In particular, dealing with photon-click patterns D in what follows, we use either the acceptance rule (8) when S is taken to be the *total time* of registering all the clicks, or the rule (7) when S is chosen to be the *histogram* of interclick intervals, with δ then denoting the L2 norm.

Generally, the challenge in performing ABC lies in choosing the summary statistics and then subsequently setting an appropriate threshold. It is not necessarily obvious what summary statistics are sufficient and, moreover, how tight the threshold should be to allow efficient sampling. As such, calibration may be necessary before the algorithm can be implemented on real data. Nonetheless, let us emphasize again that, once performed, the posterior can then be generated quickly without the need to compute the likelihood, no matter the complexity of the model, as long as a dense library of detection datasets can be *a priori* prepared—see Fig. 1(b).

The ABC algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1. Given a dataset D representing the observed measurement data, we wish to know the value of the parameter θ with which it was generated. We begin by loading a sufficiently large library of datasets \mathcal{D}' , each of which is labeled with its corresponding value of θ within the range Θ we wish to consider. Then, we repeat the procedure ν times, sampling a dataset $D'(\theta)$, without replacement, from the library \mathcal{D}' . If the summary statistics of the sampled dataset, $S(D'(\theta))$, are within ϵ of those of the observed dataset, $S(D)$, as in Eq. (7), we accept the sample and account for its contribution to the reconstructed posterior distribution. In particular, we add an element to the bin associated with the parameter value θ labeling $D'(\theta)$. Finally, we

ALGORITHM 1. Summary of ABC.

```

input  $D, \mathcal{D}' = \text{Library}[D'(\theta), \theta \in \Theta]$ 
for  $i$  in  $\nu$  do
  Select random  $D'(\theta)$  from the library.
  if  $\delta(S(D'(\theta)), S(D)) \leq \epsilon$  then
     $\text{bin}_\theta = \text{bin}_\theta + 1$ 
  end if
end for
Normalise(bin)

```

normalize the distribution according to the total number of accepted samples (out of all ν) and the bin width we assumed in coarse-graining the parameter values.

III. UNRAVELING DISSIPATIVE DYNAMICS OF CONTINUOUSLY MONITORED QUANTUM SYSTEMS

We consider quantum systems whose dissipative dynamics can be described by a master equation of the so-called Gorini-Kossakowski-Sudarshan-Lindblad form, typically referred to as being Markovian [74], i.e.,

$$\dot{\rho} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} [H, \rho] + \sum_n \Gamma_n \left(L_n \rho L_n^\dagger - \frac{1}{2} [L_n^\dagger L_n, \rho]_+ \right), \quad (9)$$

where $\rho \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H}_d)$ is then the density matrix representing the (d -dimensional) system at any given time. The Hamiltonian H describes the internal evolution of the system, while the interaction of the system with the bath is described by the Lindblad operators $\{L_n\}$, with rates Γ_n . This equation models the *ensemble-average* evolution of a quantum system, i.e., not distinguishing individual trajectories but rather averaging over them. If we have a specific measurement record, as in Fig. 1(a), we must adapt it to include stochastic elements.

In this paper, we shall consider jump-like processes. As such, a natural way to rewrite Eq. (9) is

$$\dot{\rho} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^\dagger \right] + \sum_n \Gamma_n L_n \rho L_n^\dagger, \quad (10)$$

where $H_{\text{cond}} = H - \sum_n (i\hbar/2) \Gamma_n L_n^\dagger L_n$ is a “conditional” non-Hermitian Hamiltonian that describes the effect of the Hamiltonian and processes not leading to excitation in the bath. The remaining terms correspond to interactions with the bath. In particular, we point out that the evolution of a system conditioned upon no leakage into the bath can be described by

$$\dot{\rho}_0 = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^\dagger \right], \quad (11)$$

with ρ_0 being the unnormalized density matrix, whose trace is the probability of such an evolution, in what is

known as the quantum-jump approach [47–51]. Motivated by this, we take this *unraveling* and write a stochastic master equation, where we distinguish between *accessible* decays (e.g., photons counted by a detector) and *inaccessible* decays (e.g., photons missed by a detector, processes that cannot be detected), leading to

$$d\rho = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}\rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^\dagger \right] dt + \sum_{n \in \text{accessible}} \mathcal{J}_n(\rho) + \sum_{n \notin \text{accessible}} \Gamma_n L_n \rho L_n^\dagger dt, \quad (12)$$

with the jump-process superoperator

$$\mathcal{J}_n(\rho) = \Gamma_n \text{Tr} \{ L_n^\dagger L_n \rho \} \rho dt + \left(\frac{L_n \rho L_n^\dagger}{\text{Tr} (L_n^\dagger L_n \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t^n, \quad (13)$$

where dN_t^n are increments of a Poisson process, having the physical interpretation of a random variable that represents counts over the infinitesimal time dt of an emission, with an expectation value given by [28]

$$\langle dN_t^{(n)} \rangle = \Gamma_n \text{Tr} \{ L_n^\dagger L_n \rho \} dt. \quad (14)$$

The size of each expectation value (labeled by n) gives the respective weight of a jump from the Lindblad operator L_n . We call such an unraveling the *observed unraveling*. Note that averaging over the stochastic elements restores the ensemble average provided by the standard master equation in Eq. (9).

With this in mind, we can equivalently consider an unraveling of all decay channels, both accessible and inaccessible, as pictured in the right of Fig. 1(a). In this case, we obtain a stochastic element for all channels, leading to the *full unraveling*:

$$d\rho = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}\rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^\dagger \right] dt + \sum_n \mathcal{J}_n(\rho), \quad (15)$$

which, despite including channels that are not necessarily physical, provides a useful tool in modeling the dynamics of the system. Following the quantum-jump approach [47–49], we only need to simulate the no-jump part of the dynamics to track a trajectory, while applying the stochastic “jump” terms whenever they occur. Taking into account inaccessible channels, the evolution is a modification of

Eq. (11), i.e.,

$$\dot{\rho}_{0,\text{acc}} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}\rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^\dagger \right] + \sum_{n \notin \text{accessible}} \Gamma_n L_n \rho L_n^\dagger, \quad (16)$$

where $\rho_{0,\text{acc}}$ is the unnormalized density matrix conditioned on no accessible jumps. The evolution can thus be described entirely by Eq. (16).

Solving such an equation is numerically challenging for most quantum systems due to the size of the density matrix needed for complex systems. Instead, we could work with Eq. (11), where the system remains in a pure state at all times, provided we then subsequently average over the inaccessible channels. This represents a computational advantage, as only a d -dimensional state vector needs to be simulated, rather than a $d \times d$ density matrix. For large d , this represents an important speed-up. When using Monte Carlo methods [50,51], if we retain only the information about the observed channels and average over the unobserved channels, we restore the same results as using the ensemble evolution over inaccessible bath interactions.

IV. SYSTEMS CONSIDERED AND THEIR QUANTUM TRAJECTORIES

In this section we will introduce the physical models of the systems we shall consider for inference. In particular, we shall show how quantum trajectories that are based on these systems and represent the measured photon-click patterns can be generated and analyzed using the theory of the previous section.

A. Two-level atom

We first consider a simple system that we can analyze analytically straightforwardly. The advantage of this is that as analytical results can be easily attained, the performance of the ABC algorithm can be tested efficiently for a range of values when we perform the analysis later. In particular, we consider a two-level atom subject to semiclassical driving with Rabi frequency Ω and detuning Δ , whose Hamiltonian then reads [74]

$$H^{\text{atom}} = -\hbar\Delta\sigma^+\sigma^- + \frac{\hbar\Omega}{2}(\sigma^- + \sigma^+), \quad (17)$$

where σ^+ and σ^- are the atomic raising and lowering operators, respectively. When coupled to a free radiation field under the Born-Markov and rotating-wave approximations [74], the atom evolves according to the master equation

$$\dot{\rho} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} [H^{\text{atom}}, \rho] + \Gamma \left(\sigma^- \rho \sigma^+ - \frac{1}{2} [\sigma^+ \sigma^-, \rho]_+ \right), \quad (18)$$

which is of the (Markovian) form (9). For this system, the conditional Hamiltonian takes the form

$$H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{atom}} = H^{\text{atom}} - \frac{i\hbar\Gamma}{2}\sigma^+\sigma^-, \quad (19)$$

with the conditional (no-jump) evolution given by

$$\dot{\rho}_0 = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{atom}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{atom}\dagger} \right]. \quad (20)$$

For this simple system, we consider perfect photon detection, meaning there are no unobserved jumps and no inaccessible decay channels. Thus, the stochastic master equation is

$$d\rho = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{atom}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{atom}\dagger} \right] dt + \mathcal{J}_{\text{atom}}(\rho), \quad (21)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{\text{atom}}(\rho) &= \Gamma \text{Tr} \{ \sigma^+ \sigma^- \rho \} dt \\ &+ \left(\frac{\sigma^- \rho \sigma^+}{\text{Tr}(\sigma^+ \sigma^- \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

and weight

$$\langle dN_t \rangle = \Gamma \text{Tr} \{ \sigma^+ \sigma^- \rho \} dt. \quad (23)$$

A two-level atom has the useful property that, upon emission, it always returns to its ground state. As a result, its emission profile constitutes an example of a *renewal process* that is then fully characterized by the *waiting-time distribution* [75], i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} w(\tau) d\tau &= P(\text{no click in } [0, \tau]) \\ &\times P(\text{click in } [\tau, \tau + d\tau] | \text{no click in } [0, \tau]). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Substituting the two probabilities above, we can write this as [30]

$$w(\tau) d\tau = \text{Tr}[\rho_0(\tau)] \frac{\Gamma \rho_0^{11}(\tau) d\tau}{\text{Tr}[\rho_0(\tau)]} = \Gamma \rho_0^{11}(\tau) d\tau. \quad (25)$$

Following Ref. [30], but allowing for nonzero detuning Δ , we solve Eq. (20) and obtain the solution for $\rho_0^{11}(t)$. Hence, using Eq. (25), we can directly read off the analytic expression for the waiting-time distribution as [72]

$$\begin{aligned} w(\tau) &= \frac{\Omega^2}{\Gamma\sqrt{\Xi}} e^{-(\Gamma\tau/2)} \\ &\times \left[\cosh\left(\frac{\Gamma\tau}{2}\sqrt{\zeta_+}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{\Gamma\tau}{2}\sqrt{\zeta_-}\right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

after defining $\Xi := \frac{1}{4} + 2\chi_- + 4\chi_+^2$ and $\zeta_{\pm} := \sqrt{\Xi} \pm (\frac{1}{2} - 2\chi_+)$ with $\chi_{\pm} := (\Delta^2 \pm \Omega^2)/\Gamma^2$. In Fig. 2(a), we plot the resulting waiting-time distribution (26) as a function of time t for various detunings Δ .

B. Optomechanical system

The second physical model we consider is an optomechanical system. The relevant Hamiltonian for an optomechanical system is [19]

$$\begin{aligned} H^{\text{OM}} &= -\hbar\Delta a^\dagger a + \hbar\omega_M b^\dagger b + \frac{\hbar\Omega}{2} (a + a^\dagger) \\ &+ \hbar g a^\dagger a (b + b^\dagger), \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where a (b) is the bosonic annihilation operator for the photonic (phononic) mode of the system, Δ is the laser detuning, ω_M is the mechanical frequency, Ω is the laser Rabi frequency, and g is the optomechanical coupling strength.

Unlike the atom, we now consider two interacting quantum systems with multiple decay channels. The optical part of the system decays through photon emission, while the mechanical part interacts with a thermal bath, leading to both phonon emission and absorption. Following the procedure in Sec. III, we write a (thermal) master equation as [74]

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\rho} &= -\frac{i}{\hbar} [H^{\text{OM}}, \rho] + \kappa \left(a \rho a^\dagger - \frac{1}{2} [a^\dagger a, \rho]_+ \right) \\ &+ \gamma (\bar{m} + 1) \left(b \rho b^\dagger - \frac{1}{2} [b^\dagger b, \rho]_+ \right) \\ &+ \gamma \bar{m} \left(b^\dagger \rho b - \frac{1}{2} [bb^\dagger, \rho]_+ \right). \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

We label the optical decay rate as κ and the mechanical decay rate as γ , assuming the thermal bath interacting with the mechanical system has a mean occupation number given by $\bar{m} = [\exp(\hbar\omega_M/k_B T) - 1]^{-1}$ [74,76]. Next, we write a conditional Hamiltonian

$$H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{OM}} = H^{\text{OM}} - \frac{i\hbar}{2} (\kappa a^\dagger a + \gamma (\bar{m} + 1) b^\dagger b + \gamma \bar{m} b b^\dagger). \quad (29)$$

We now have only one observed decay channel, through finite-efficiency photon counting. This leads to an observed unraveling of

$$\begin{aligned} d\rho &= -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{OM}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{OM}\dagger} \right] dt + \mathcal{J}_{\kappa_d}(\rho) \\ &+ (\kappa_d a \rho a^\dagger + \gamma (\bar{m} + 1) b \rho b^\dagger + \gamma \bar{m} b^\dagger \rho b) dt, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

with a jump term

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{\kappa_d}(\rho) &= \kappa_d \text{Tr} \{ a^\dagger a \rho \} \rho dt + \left(\frac{a \rho a^\dagger}{\text{Tr}(a^\dagger a \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t^{\kappa_d}, \\ \langle dN_t^{\kappa_d} \rangle &= \kappa_d \text{Tr} \{ a^\dagger a \rho \} dt. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

FIG. 2. Waiting-time distribution for a two-level atom. The analytic form is presented in (a) for a number of different values of the detuning Δ . In (b),(c), we compare the waiting-time distribution with the normalized time-binned photon counts averaged over numerically generated trajectories for $\Delta = 1$ and $\Delta = 7$, respectively. In both (b) and (c), we see strong agreement between the numerical and analytical results; however, the variance among the trajectories is higher in (c), as marked by the error bars. This indicates that a larger number of samples is required to reconstruct $w(t)$, which naively implies reduced efficiency for sampling-based methods such as ABC. For each value of Δ (expressed in units of Γ), we set $\Omega = 2\Gamma$ in Eq. (17).

In these equations, we have introduced separate decay rates for the detected (κ_d) and lost (κ_l) photons, such that $\kappa_d + \kappa_l = \kappa$ [76]. Finally, we can write the full unraveling as

$$d\rho = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{OM}} \rho - \rho H_{\text{cond}}^{\text{OM}\dagger} \right] dt + \mathcal{J}_{\kappa_d}(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\kappa_l}(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\gamma^-}(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\gamma^+}(\rho), \quad (32)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{\kappa_l}(\rho) &= \kappa_l \text{Tr} \{ a^\dagger a \rho \} \rho dt + \left(\frac{a \rho a^\dagger}{\text{Tr}(a^\dagger a \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t^{\kappa_l}, \\ \mathcal{J}_{\gamma^-}(\rho) &= \gamma (\bar{m} + 1) \text{Tr} \{ b^\dagger b \rho \} \rho dt \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{b \rho b^\dagger}{\text{Tr}(b^\dagger b \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t^{\gamma^-}, \\ \mathcal{J}_{\gamma^+}(\rho) &= \gamma \bar{m} \text{Tr} \{ b b^\dagger \rho \} \rho dt + \left(\frac{b^\dagger \rho b}{\text{Tr}(b b^\dagger \rho)} - \rho \right) dN_t^{\gamma^+}, \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

with weights

$$\begin{aligned} \langle dN_t^{\kappa_l} \rangle &= \kappa \text{Tr} \{ a^\dagger a \rho \} dt, \\ \langle dN_t^{\gamma^-} \rangle &= \gamma (\bar{m} + 1) \text{Tr} \{ b^\dagger b \rho \} dt, \\ \langle dN_t^{\gamma^+} \rangle &= \gamma \bar{m} \text{Tr} \{ b b^\dagger \rho \} dt. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

We emphasize again that the stochastic trajectory based only on physical observations must be computed using Eq.

(30), while Eq. (32) provides the full unraveling involving unobserved jumps that have to be averaged over to restore the real dynamics. Nevertheless, Eq. (32) gives a pure evolution that is computationally simple to solve and can be effectively used to generate click patterns of detected photons (i.e., the times at which $dN_t^{\kappa_d} = 1$) by simply ignoring the records of other inaccessible jump processes ($dN_t^{\kappa_l}$, $dN_t^{\gamma^-}$, $dN_t^{\gamma^+}$).

1. Linear regime

If the coupling is weak compared to the driving strength of the system, a linearization of the dynamics can be performed without significantly affecting the precision of the dynamics. In particular, the optical and mechanical modes can be transformed into

$$a \rightarrow \alpha + \tilde{a}, \quad (35a)$$

$$b \rightarrow \beta + \tilde{b}, \quad (35b)$$

where α and β are complex numbers and \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} are annihilation operators acting on a quantum fluctuation. Applying the standard input-output formalism [19,77], one may derive the Langevin equations for both the classical contributions,

$$\dot{\alpha} = \left(i\Delta' - \frac{\kappa}{2} \right) \alpha - \frac{i\Omega}{2}, \quad (36a)$$

$$\dot{\beta} = \left(-i\omega_M - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \beta - ig|\alpha|^2, \quad (36b)$$

and the quantum contributions,

$$\dot{\tilde{a}} = \left(i\Delta' - \frac{\kappa}{2} \right) \tilde{a} - ig\alpha \left(\tilde{b} + \tilde{b}^\dagger \right) - ig\tilde{a} \left(\tilde{b} + \tilde{b}^\dagger \right), \quad (37a)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{b}} = \left(-i\omega_M - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \tilde{b} - ig \left(\alpha^* \tilde{a} + \alpha \tilde{a}^\dagger \right) - ig\tilde{a}^\dagger \tilde{a} - \sqrt{\gamma} \tilde{b}_{\text{in}}, \quad (37b)$$

to the modes with the effective detuning $\Delta' := \Delta - g(\beta + \beta^*)$. Consistent with Eq. (28), no noise terms appear in the optical part of the quantum fluctuations (37a), while thermal fluctuations are accounted for due to \tilde{b}_{in} in the mechanical part (37b).

For common parameter choices—i.e., strong driving and weak coupling—the “classical part” is vastly greater than the “quantum part,” i.e., $|\alpha| \gg \langle \tilde{a} \rangle$ and $|\beta| \gg \langle \tilde{b} \rangle$. In this case, the nonlinear terms can be further dropped in the quantum part of the Langevin equations (37) [19,77], effectively corresponding to a linearized version of the Hamiltonian (27) that reads [77]

$$H^{\text{lin}} = -\hbar\Delta' \tilde{a}^\dagger \tilde{a} + \hbar\omega_M \tilde{b}^\dagger \tilde{b} + (G\tilde{a}^\dagger + G^*\tilde{a}) \left(\tilde{b} + \tilde{b}^\dagger \right), \quad (38)$$

where $G := \alpha g$.

This Hamiltonian (38) can be used to describe the quantum part of the evolution, whereas the classical contributions to the optical and mechanical modes, α and β , should be computed independently by solving Eqs. (36). Typically, however, these quickly attain their *steady-state* values, α_{ss} and β_{ss} , which can always be determined numerically. Hence, to facilitate the analysis of the optomechanical system in the linear regime in what follows, we shall initialize both the optical and mechanical modes in their classical steady states. As a result, since the linear approximation requires the classical contribution to the modes to be much larger than quantum fluctuations, we expect both optical and mechanical modes to remain approximately in coherent states, $|\alpha_{\text{ss}}\rangle$ and $|\beta_{\text{ss}}\rangle$, at all times.

We verify this intuition for the optical degree of freedom in Fig. 3 by considering the probability of detecting no photons over time, $P_0(t)$. On one hand, we solve numerically the exact dynamics (28) for the true Hamiltonian, H^{OM} in Eq. (27), in which case the no-photon probability is given by $P_0(t) = \text{Tr} \{ \rho_{0,\text{acc}}(t) \}$. To perform the numerics, we take a truncated Fock space for both the optical and mechanical Hilbert spaces [76]. The truncation must not be too severe such that important dynamics are lost, but it must result in a density matrix that is not too large to be computationally solvable. On the other hand, we consider the approximate solution, i.e., we neglect the quantum

FIG. 3. Optomechanical system in the linear regime. The probability of observing no photons, P_0 , as a function of time (units of κ^{-1}) for two different values of detuning Δ (units of κ) computed using the full numeric solution (solid lines) and the analytic linearized approximation discarding the quantum fluctuations (dashed lines). In each case, the system is initialized in the stationary state. The agreement between the two solutions demonstrates that the system remains approximately in a coherent state at all times, and as such, a Poissonian distribution for the number of photon clicks over time is expected. Other system parameters are set to $9\kappa_l = \kappa_d$, $\bar{m} = 1$, $10g = \omega_M/6 = \kappa$, $\Omega = 2\omega_M$, and $\Gamma = \omega_M/1200$.

part of the dynamics (37) and assume only the classical contribution (36), in which case $P_0(t) = \exp(-\kappa_d |\alpha(t)|^2 t)$. Moreover, as we take the system to initially be in the stationary state, Fig. 3 depicts $P_0(t) = \exp(-\kappa_d |\alpha_{\text{ss}}|^2 t)$ which, indeed, up to negligible precision, coincides with the exact numerical solution.

2. Nonlinear regime

In a nonlinear optomechanical system, we have stronger coupling, meaning that the linearization procedure highlighted previously is no longer valid. As such, there are no analytic results available, and numerical modeling is required. We again impose a truncated Fock space and use the same methods [76] as done previously to obtain the full numerical solution in the linear regime; however, there is one key feature of such systems that we highlight and take advantage of in the following. In particular, we look at the energy spectrum of a nonlinear optomechanical system. This can be written as [76,78]

$$E(n_{\text{cav}}, n_{\text{mech}}) = -\hbar\Delta n_{\text{cav}} + \hbar\omega_M n_{\text{mech}} - \hbar \frac{g^2}{\omega_M} n_{\text{cav}}^2, \quad (39)$$

where n_{cav} and n_{mech} are the occupation numbers of the cavity and mechanics, respectively. Let us now consider

what happens to the overall energy of the system whenever a photon is absorbed or emitted from the cavity. In particular, we define special values of the detuning as

$$\Delta_n := -ng^2/\omega_M. \quad (40)$$

Then, for $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, the first and third terms in Eq. (39) cancel for the cavity occupation number $n_{\text{cav}} = n$. This means that transitioning from n photons in the cavity to 0 results in no energy change. Therefore, this transition is resonant and energetically favorable for the dynamics.

In this paper, we focus on two particular values of detuning for the nonlinear system. We choose $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ in Eq. (40). In doing so, we create the resonant transition of the ground state with the first and second excited states, respectively. This creates interesting photon statistics: for the $n = 1$ case, we see regular single-photon emission, whereas for the $n = 2$ case, we see highly bunched light [76,78]. These photon statistics clearly have very different properties, and they should thus be distinguishable when trying to infer the value of the detuning. We analyze the photon statistics further in the next subsection.

C. Statistics of emitted photons

We now analyze the behavior of the photon statistics for both the two-level atom and the optomechanical system introduced above. A natural way to analyze this is through the *second-order correlation function*

$$g^{(2)}(t_1, t_2) := \frac{p(t_1, t_2)}{p(t_1)p(t_2)} = \frac{p(t_2|t_1)}{p(t_2)}, \quad (41)$$

where $t_2 \geq t_1$ and the probabilities are those of detecting a photon at the given times. Typically, we consider t_1 to be a time in the stationary state, meaning that t_2 can be thought of as merely a delay time τ_d after the first emission. In this case, the correlation function can be written as $g^{(2)}(\tau_d)$. As throughout this work, the unknown parameter to be inferred is the detuning of the driving, Δ , and we are interested in how the photon statistics vary as a function of Δ . Hence, we depict in Fig. 4, and discuss in more detail below, the behaviors of the $g^{(2)}$ -function for both systems and the relevant detuning values.

As well as the correlation functions, we shall also consider the average time to emit a fixed number of photons for each system. This is a quantity that will clearly vary with the detuning and thus serve as a suitable summary statistic for later performing ABC. The total time to emit N photons can be expressed simply as the sum of the waiting time for N photons, i.e.,

$$t_N := \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta t_i, \quad (42)$$

where Δt_i is the time between subsequent $(i - 1)$ th and i th photon emissions.

FIG. 4. Stationary-state $g^{(2)}$ -function for the systems considered. For the two-level atom, oscillations are observed with their strength proportional to the detuning—the atom resets itself to the ground state and subsequently takes longer to reset for larger detunings. Nevertheless, the behavior remains relatively simple. For the linear optomechanical system, the behavior is even simpler, as expected from the analysis in Sec. IV B 1. The $g^{(2)}$ -function stays almost exactly at 1 for all times. Finally, for the nonlinear optomechanical system, we see the complex behavior predicted from the bunching effects described in Sec. IV B 2 and in Refs. [76,78]. The correlations may last for long times in such systems, demonstrating the complex nature of the statistics, which are not effectively Poissonian within the considered time interval. For the two-level atom, we take the parameters as in Fig. 2, and for the linear optomechanical system, we take the parameters as in Fig. 3. The nonlinear optomechanical system has parameters $9\kappa_l = \kappa_d$ and $\bar{m} = 1$, as for the linear system, but now $g/4 = \omega_M/4\sqrt{2} = \kappa$, and $\Omega = 0.3/\omega_M$, $\Gamma = 10^{-3}\omega_M$ for the remaining parameters, as in Refs. [76,78].

Considering any system that resets itself into a fixed state after an emission event, i.e., a renewal process, the expectation value for t_N and its variance are determined by the waiting-time distribution $w(\tau)$ [75]. In particular, as shown in the Appendix, it is straightforward to show that $\langle t_N \rangle = N\langle \Delta t \rangle$ and $\text{Var}[t_N] = N \text{Var}[\Delta t]$, where

$$\langle \Delta t \rangle = \int_0^\infty d\tau \tau w(\tau), \quad (43a)$$

$$\text{Var}[\Delta t] = \int_0^\infty d\tau (\tau - \langle \Delta t \rangle)^2 w(\tau), \quad (43b)$$

are the average waiting time for a single click and its variance, respectively.

It is convenient to inspect the *signal-to-noise ratio* (SNR) γ that is defined via both (43a) and (43b) as [79]

$$\gamma := \frac{\langle \Delta t \rangle^2}{\text{Var}[\Delta t]} \stackrel{\text{r.p.}}{=} \frac{\langle t_N \rangle^2}{N \text{Var}[t_N]}, \quad (44)$$

FIG. 5. Total time t_N to emit a fixed number N of photons for each system considered, averaged over 2000 numerically generated trajectories for different values of detuning. A monotonic behavior for (a) the two-level atom and (b) the linear optomechanical system is observed, in contrast to a highly multivariate function for the nonlinear system in (c), where the key detunings, $\Delta_{n=1}$ (left) and $\Delta_{n=2}$ (right), are highlighted with dashed vertical lines. The standard deviation of the sampled trajectories is marked by the shaded area. The insets of (a) and (b) present the expected analytic behavior (dark dashed line) for the SNR, γ defined in Eq. (44), as a function of Δ , compared with the numerical prediction [right-hand side of Eq. (44)] obtained by averaging over the simulated N -click trajectories (faint solid line). These indicate strong agreement between the numerics and theory, suggesting good reliability of the prepared library of trajectories.

which, for a renewal process (r.p.), should also be recovered by considering a series of N clicks and evaluating the expression above. Note that γ is unity for any renewal process such that the variance of the average waiting time is equal to the square of its mean. In particular, this is the case for a Poissonian system whose waiting-time distribution is exponential—a manifestation of the Markov property for the underlying stochastic process [75].

When evaluating the t_N -statistic (42) (and indeed simulating all trajectories of the systems), we initialize the system in a simple initial state, rather than the stationary state. Nevertheless, due to the Ergodic principle, these two statistics are relevant, as all trajectories we consider will be averaged over long enough times, and we shall consider a large enough ensemble, so that all statistics are consistent. This can also be thought of as allowing N to be sufficiently large, such that almost all of the clicks are independent of any initial state. We show the expected value for the total time to emit N photons in Fig. 5, based on averaging over the library of trajectories and also the analytic solutions, where available. We now discuss each physical system individually.

1. Two-level atom

The two-level atom is the simplest of the systems that we consider. The waiting-time distribution fully characterizes when the next emission will occur because of the common resetting to the ground state. We analyze this by averaging over a library of trajectories for two sample

detunings in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c). In particular, we find that the trajectories reproduce the waiting time on average very well; however, the variance increases with increasing detuning. This is due to the flattening of the waiting-time distribution, which itself is caused by the reduction in oscillation between the ground and excited state at higher detunings.

In the case of a two-level atom, whenever a photon is emitted, the atom is reset into its ground state. This process must yield correlations in the photon statistics, which are affected by the value of the detuning. This is seen in the oscillations of the $g^{(2)}$ -function in Fig. 4, which are stronger for the higher value of detuning. Nevertheless, as the state resetting is consistent throughout the entire evolution, the waiting time, and thus the intensity of emitted light, is primarily determined by the characteristics of the data.

Moreover, using Eqs. (26) and (43), we calculate analytically the expected waiting time for the emission of N photons and its variance, which are respectively given by [72]

$$\langle \Delta t \rangle_{\text{atom}} = \frac{\Gamma^2 + 4\Delta^2 + 2\Omega^2}{\Gamma\Omega^2}, \quad (45a)$$

$$\text{Var}[\Delta t]_{\text{atom}} = \frac{(\Gamma^2 + 4\Delta^2)^2 - 2(\Gamma^2 - 12\Delta^2)\Omega^2 + 4\Omega^2}{\Gamma^2\Omega^4}. \quad (45b)$$

The expression for the waiting time (45a) is compared with the one computed numerically using the library of trajectories in Fig. 5(a). We see good agreement between the two methodologies and, as one would expect, observe quadratic growth as the detuning increases. Importantly, we therefore conclude that this quantity will serve well as a summary statistic for ABC in the later sections, despite it ignoring the effect of correlations.

Similarly, using the expression (45b), we present the SNR (44) within the inset of Fig. 5(a). We see that γ varies as a function of Δ , which is to be expected for a renewal process with a waiting-time distribution that is *not* exponential [75]. As such, the performance of ABC according to this statistic will differ for different values of the detuning.

2. Linear optomechanical system

The linear optomechanical system is more complex, but, as discussed in Sec. IV B 1, the dynamics are, to a good approximation, those of a perturbed coherent state. As such, upon reaching a stationary state, the system effectively no longer evolves, even under photon emission. This is shown both by the agreement of our approximation with the numerical solution in Fig. 3 and the $g^{(2)}$ -function in Fig. 4, where we see that the system remains approximately classical at all times (i.e., $\forall \tau \geq 0 : g^{(2)}(\tau) \approx 1$), for both selected values of detuning. As such, recalling Fig. 3, the exponent of the exponential waiting-time distribution—and hence the (inverse of) the average waiting time (43a)—contains all the information about the system.

We also see a monotonic increase in the total emission time t_N in Fig. 5(b), further confirming the expected suitability of this statistic for ABC. As the system approximately resets into a fixed state upon emission (as the dynamics are close to coherent), both t_N and its variance should be almost exactly N times the expressions in (43). Still, as we do not have the exact form of $w(t)$ here, we cannot provide an analytic solution. Unlike the two-level atom, however, we have an (approximately) coherent-light emitter, where the waiting times between photon-click events follow an (approximately) exponential distribution. This implies that the SNR (44) should be close to unity, regardless of the value of detuning, as verified within the inset of Fig. 5(b).

3. Nonlinear optomechanical system

The nonlinear system is far more complex than the two previous examples. Not only is there no analytic solution, but the system cannot even be approximately assumed to reset itself to a common state after each emission. Moreover, the effect of a jump is highly nontrivial, resulting in correlated photon statistics. The reason for this can be seen by analyzing Eq. (39) more carefully.

When the dynamics are resonant, i.e., in the $n = 1, 2$ regimes described previously, the system favors transitioning to and from the ground state and the n th level in the cavity. For the $n = 1$ case, this means that the optical part of the dynamics will favor emitting single photons, effectively acting as a two-level atom. For the $n = 2$ case, the system will typically emit photons in pairs. This is due to the cavity rapidly decaying from the 2-photon state to the ground state. This leads to a pronounced bunching effect, evident in the noticeably high $g^{(2)}$ -function shown in Fig. 4. These correlations are significant in the photon statistics and should therefore be taken into account to fully characterize the emission profile.

This is further shown in the total emission time in Fig. 5(c), which exhibits a nonmonotonic dependence on the detuning. We therefore expect that this will limit the performance of ABC using this statistic. Nevertheless, there is a well-isolated minimum around $\Delta_{n=1}$ that, when approached from above or below, should still provide sufficient information about the detuning Δ by inspecting the total emission time t_N ; however, we note that the observed variance $\text{Var}[t_N]$ is nonzero at $\Delta = \Delta_{n=1}$, so we expect that the t_N -statistic will not be as informative as in the cases of the two-level atom or linear optomechanics near $\Delta = 0$.

V. PARAMETER INFERENCE AND THE APPLICATION OF THE ABC ALGORITHM

In this section, we apply the ABC algorithm to the exemplary systems analyzed in the previous section. For each system, we first identify the summary statistics used and then verify the performance of the algorithm against the true posterior obtained by analytical or numerical methods. As stated previously, we take the detuning Δ to be the unknown parameter throughout, over which we are to obtain the posterior. For all systems, we perform ABC with summary statistics that are expected to be sufficient. In the case of the nonlinear optomechanical system, we begin by using the total emission time as a summary statistic to verify its limitations. We then enhance the effectiveness of ABC by switching to the histogram of waiting times as a summary statistic, which is importantly capable of capturing photon-bunching (quantum) effects.

A. Benchmarking the performance of ABC

1. Prior choice

In what follows, we take a flat prior distribution across the parameter space. In doing so, we ensure that any results we obtain are not biased by any preference for a particular true parameter value. Moreover, as the ABC algorithm is affected by the prior as the proposal distribution, this choice ensures that we are not just reproducing the posterior by only selecting samples from the correct region.

2. Quantifying the error of ABC

To quantify how well the ABC algorithm performs, we compute the *fidelity* of the posteriors it produces by evaluating the relevant Bhattacharyya coefficient:

$$F[p_{\text{post}}, p_{\text{ABC}}|D_t] := \int d\Delta \sqrt{p_{\text{post}}(\Delta|D_t)} \sqrt{p_{\text{ABC}}(\Delta|D_t)}, \quad (46)$$

where $p_{\text{post}}(\Delta|D_t)$ denotes the true posterior, obtained analytically for the two-level atom or numerically for the optomechanical system, and $p_{\text{ABC}}(\Delta|D_t)$ is the posterior obtained through ABC. We show the results of this calculation in the insets of the main plots (depicting the posteriors) as a function of the *number of samples used* ν (recall the ABC algorithm, Algorithm 1), *not* the number of samples accepted. If the summary statistics are sufficient, then in the limit of an infinitely tight bound with infinitely many samples, the fidelity averaged over many trajectories should converge to 1. This is due to the definition of sufficiency in Eq. (5), meaning that, in this case, we are effectively sampling directly from the posterior [80]. Of course, with realistic numerical capabilities, it is not possible to do this, but for reasonably tight bounds and our finite library, we expect to come close to unity if the summary statistics are well chosen.

For the two-level atom, as we are able to analyze trajectories analytically, we can produce analytic posteriors with ease. In this case, to determine the average fidelity of ABC, we analyze its performance by averaging not only over multiple implementations of the ABC algorithm [also considering different thresholds ϵ in Eq. (7)] for a given photon-click trajectory, but also over distinct trajectories being observed. We do this for two different true values of the detuning Δ to illustrate the performance of the algorithm across the parameter range. For the optomechanical system, however, obtaining the true posterior is highly computationally expensive. Hence, instead of averaging over multiple trajectories, we take three exemplary trajectories for each of the two different true values of Δ and evaluate the ABC performance by averaging only over multiple implementations of the algorithm (again for different values of the threshold ϵ).

3. Optimizing the ABC algorithm

The performance of the ABC algorithms, and thus the fidelity F introduced in Eq. (46), strongly depends on the choice of threshold ϵ in Eq. (7), as well as the number of samples ν considered. As more samples are used, the fidelity gradually plateaus and reaches a steady value. One may naively expect that the tighter the threshold ϵ , the better performance of the algorithm; however, this comes at the cost of requiring an increased number of samples ν to reach this plateau. We demonstrate this for all of

our fidelity plots in what follows and indeed observe that, in some cases, the tightest choice of ϵ is not optimal. This is because it results in undersampling, even when the maximal number of samples ν considered. In most cases, however, we observe that, given the large number of trajectories we possess in the library, the use of an excessively large number of samples actually results in oversampling. For the two-level atom and linear optomechanical system, we evaluate the performance up to $\nu = 2 \times 10^5$, whereas for the nonlinear system we use up to $\nu = 4 \times 10^5$. In this regard, our results allow us to optimize the ABC algorithm in each case by identifying the number of samples ν required given a particular threshold ϵ .

B. Two-level atom

For the two-level atom, the posterior may be obtained analytically, meaning that, in principle, the use of the ABC algorithm is not advantageous; however, as we are able to obtain analytic posteriors cheaply, we can benchmark the performance of the ABC algorithm by applying it to a large number of true posteriors straightforwardly.

1. Summary statistic: total time

Recalling Sec. IV C 1, a simple summary statistic should be enough to reproduce the posterior due to the emission profile constituting a renewal process. In particular, the *total time* to emit a certain number of photons, t_N in Eq. (42), should be reasonably characteristic of any dataset. It is also a monotonic function of Δ [see Fig. 5(a)], and it should thus be able to effectively distinguish between its different values. For the two-level atom, we take the number of emitted photons to be $N = 200$, so our summary statistic becomes $S(D_t) = t_{N=200}(D_t)$.

2. Results

Using this summary statistic, we apply the ABC algorithm and present the results in Fig. 6 for a range of different acceptance thresholds ϵ . We observe that for two different true values of the detuning, $\Delta = 1, 7 (\times \Gamma)$, the algorithm is capable of reproducing the true posterior to a good approximation. For $\Delta = 1$, the algorithm saturates its potential very quickly and to a high fidelity, with looser thresholds achieving this more quickly but reaching worse overall fidelity. For $\Delta = 7$, some errors start to appear, due to the flattening of the weighting-time distribution—see Fig. 2(c)—which makes it less sensitive to variations in Δ . Although this indicates that more sophisticated statistics accounting for multitime correlations are necessary to achieve better performance at $\Delta = 7$, the ABC algorithm still works reasonably well.

In the insets of Fig. 6, we show the average fidelity (46) between the posteriors generated through ABC and the corresponding true posteriors. We average over 20 different

FIG. 6. ABC performance for the two-level atom using the total time taken to emit $N = 200$ photons as the summary statistic, for two different values of detuning: $\Delta = 1\Gamma$ (left) and $\Delta = 7\Gamma$ (right). The main plots depict the ABC-based posteriors (in color) for different values of the acceptance threshold ϵ , which become increasingly close to the true posterior (black) as the threshold is decreased, provided that a sufficiently large number of samples is used. All the posteriors shown are for one implementation of the ABC algorithm on a specific photon-click trajectory D_t ; however, we test this further by averaging over 20 different trajectories (and ten different implementations of ABC) for both values of Δ , and we show the average fidelity $\langle F \rangle_{\text{traj}}$ as a function of the number of samples used, ν , within the insets. These demonstrate that the ABC algorithm quickly reaches its performance limit with relatively few samples. System parameters are as in Fig. 2, and the library of trajectories used can be found in Ref. [81].

trajectories (i.e., true posteriors) and ten unique implementations of ABC for each trajectory to evaluate the average performance of the algorithm. We observe that the number of samples ν required to saturate the performance of ABC is greater for $\Delta = 7$ than for $\Delta = 1$. Additionally, within the range of ν considered, the performance is saturated for all but the strictest acceptance threshold ϵ ; however, for $\Delta = 7$, there is hardly any improvement in the maximal average fidelity attained as ϵ is further reduced. This is a consequence of the much longer total emission times in these trajectories—recall Fig. 5(a), where $\langle t_N \rangle \approx 500(10\,000)$ for $\Delta = 1(7)$. Hence, as it is the difference between total times that is used for acceptance, for thresholds to have the same significance, these should be rescaled by a factor of approximately 20; however, we must avoid any adjustments of the ABC algorithm depending on the value of Δ , as these would require the estimated parameter to be known in advance. Hence, we are forced to select a value of ϵ that remains sufficiently tight across the full range $\Delta \in [0, 10]$ —for example, from Fig. 6, we may infer $\epsilon = 20\kappa^{-1}$ as an ideal candidate for all-round performance (given $\nu = 20 \times 10^4$ samples).

Lastly, let us comment on the bias exhibited by the posteriors in Fig. 6, which naively seem to be shifted to the left (right) for $\Delta = 1$ (7). This, however, is a standard artefact of Bayesian inference when evaluating performance based on a single trajectory. Moreover, as our summary statistic based on the total time is not exactly sufficient, it may also introduce some systematic errors. Nevertheless,

when multiple trajectories are analyzed—e.g., to compute the average fidelities in Fig. 6—we observe that the bias is washed out on average.

C. Linear optomechanical system

The linear optomechanical system requires numerical solutions to identify the true posterior distribution. Thus, the ABC algorithm provides a useful speed-up. Again, we first discuss the summary statistics employed before presenting the performance of the ABC algorithm.

1. Summary statistic: total time

In Sec. IVC 2, it was shown that the intensity of emitted light, i.e., the exponent of the exponential waiting-time distribution, should almost completely characterize the emission profile for a linear optomechanical system. Hence, the *total time* for a fixed number of photon emissions, t_N in Eq. (42), should again be sufficient as a summary statistic; however, due to the increased computational cost of simulating the dynamics, we restrict ourselves to 50 photons, i.e., $S(D_t) = t_{N=50}(D_t)$. This is (at least approximately) sufficient due to the simplicity of the exponential average waiting-time distribution, assured by the (almost) Poissonian emission profile discussed in Sec. IVC 2.

2. Results

We show the results of implementing ABC with a variety of thresholds for the linear optomechanical system in

FIG. 7. ABC performance for the linear optomechanical system using the total time taken to emit $N = 50$ photons as the summary statistic, for two different values of detuning: (a)–(c) $\Delta = -1\kappa$ and (d)–(f) $\Delta = -7\kappa$. In each plot, the ABC-based posterior distributions (different colors for different thresholds ϵ) are presented against the true posterior (black). As the latter is obtained by performing brute-force numerics, we cannot present the ABC performance averaged over different photon-click trajectories. Instead, the insets present (in contrast to Fig. 6) the fidelity (46), F , for each of the six different photon-click trajectories D_t considered (still averaged over ten implementations of ABC for each threshold). We find good agreement with the true posterior in all cases, demonstrating the validity of ABC. Moreover, the performance is satisfactory regardless of the detuning value—in line with our understanding of photon-click statistics—particularly the total time and its SNR presented in Fig. 5(b). Once again, the library of trajectories used is available in Ref. [81].

Fig. 7. We see strong agreement even for larger detuning, in line with our expectations for this summary statistic and the linear optomechanical system. This is due to the simplistic nature of the photon-emission patterns, which form an approximately exponential distribution whose exponent is monotonic in the detuning parameter—recall Fig. 5(b).

We again quantify the performance of the algorithm through the fidelity (46); however, unlike the two-level atom, obtaining true posteriors requires numerical solutions to the dynamics, which are extremely time consuming. We instead show the results of three indicative trajectories for $\Delta = -1\kappa$ in Figs. 7(a)–7(c) and for $\Delta = -7\kappa$ in Figs. 7(d)–7(f). The insets now show the fidelity averaged over ten implementations of the ABC algorithm but no longer averaged over different photon-click trajectories. Nevertheless, we see reasonable agreement for all the

trajectories considered, suggesting that the performance is relatively consistent.

In particular, we also see consistent performance for the different values of detuning. This is in agreement with expectations from the SNR γ presented in the inset of Fig. 5(b), which is mostly invariant to changes in detuning. Moreover, as the statistics form an exponential distribution, the emitted light is almost coherent with no interphoton correlations—i.e., $\forall \tau : g^{(2)}(\tau) \approx 1$ in Fig. 4, meaning that the total time for a fixed number of emissions (42) is highly informative. We therefore see improved performance compared to the two-level atom.

Contrastingly, we see that choosing the tightest threshold in the ABC algorithm, $\epsilon = 2.5$ (red) in Fig. 7, does not yield the best performance. This can be explained by the fact that we consider individual trajectories rather

FIG. 8. ABC performance for the nonlinear optomechanical system using the total time taken to emit $N = 80$ photons as the summary statistic, for two different values of detuning: (a)–(c) $\Delta = \Delta_{n=1} \approx -2.8\kappa$ and (d)–(f) $\Delta = \Delta_{n=2} \approx -5.6\kappa$. In each subplot (a)–(f), a different photon-click trajectory is considered and, as before, ABC-based posterior distributions (different colors for different thresholds ϵ) are presented against the true posterior (black). In (a)–(c), we see that ABC has reasonable performance, though it is clearly less accurate than in the case of the linear system. In (d)–(f), however, the algorithm fails to reproduce the posterior in all the cases, resulting in low fidelity (averaged over ten ABC implementations) within each inset. As expected from Fig. 5(c), the total time t_N can now no longer be considered as a sufficient summary statistic, especially around $\Delta = \Delta_{n=2}$. The library of trajectories used can be found in Ref. [81].

than averaging over many. Thus, our trajectories could be unrepresentative, in that their summary statistics are not represented well enough by the samples in our library. Therefore, we need looser thresholds to capture their behavior, unless the number of samples ν can be significantly increased. Nevertheless, comparing the overall shapes of posteriors in Fig. 7, the impact of choosing an overly tight threshold is relatively negligible.

D. Nonlinear optomechanical system

Finally, we consider the nonlinear optomechanical system. As already emphasized, the dynamics are now complex, resulting in nontrivial photon statistics. Nevertheless, we first proceed with the same summary statistics—the total emission time—to explicitly demonstrate that, as

expected, it will *not* be satisfactory, especially for detunings yielding photon-bunching effects.

1. Summary statistic: total time

We consider again the time for a fixed number of photon emissions, t_N in Eq. (42), as the summary statistic, but we increase the number of detection events to 80, meaning $S(D_t) = t_{N=80}(D_t)$. Nonetheless, as t_N is highly nonmonotonic in detuning Δ [see Fig. 5(c)], we expect such an approach to generally fail; however, as the global minimum in Fig. 5 occurs at $\Delta = \Delta_{n=1}$, we also expect Δ to still be inferable around that point. Hence, to also confirm this behavior, we again examine the performance of ABC with t_N used as the only summary statistic for the nonlinear optomechanical system.

2. Results

We present the results alongside the true posteriors obtained by numerical means in Fig. 8, as for the linear optomechanical system. For Figs. 8(a)–8(c), we set $\Delta = \Delta_{n=1}$, while for Figs. 8(d)–8(f) we set $\Delta = \Delta_{n=2}$. As expected, in the $n = 1$ regime, we see good performance from ABC, and it is capable of identifying the parameter range around $\Delta_{n=1}$ to a high degree of accuracy, but slightly mistaking it for $\Delta_{n=3} = -8.4\kappa$, where the most similar total emission times can occur—see Fig. 5(c). For the $n = 2$ regime, however, the algorithm does not reproduce the posterior, and it is only able to *eliminate* the “inferable” values of the detuning around $\Delta_{n=1}$ from the distribution.

For the $n = 1$ regime, we see that the tighter thresholds achieve better fidelities than the looser ones, meaning, unlike for the linear system, the results are in line with expectations. Moreover, they achieve this extremely quickly. For the $n = 2$ case, there is little difference in performance across the thresholds, as there are never meaningful results, even with a large number of samples. To confirm this, we run the algorithm over twice as many samples ($\nu_{\max} = 4 \times 10^5$) to ensure that the fidelity has indeed saturated, as shown in the insets of Figs. 8(d)–8(f).

3. Summary statistic: histogram of waiting times

As confirmed, the total emission time does not constitute a sufficient summary statistic for nonlinear optomechanics, as it is monotonic only within restricted ranges of the detuning parameter Δ [see Fig. 5(c)], but it is also incapable of distinguishing distinct types of interphoton correlations; however, before proposing other summary statistics, one could consider a “full-data” approach [66] with the acceptance rule (7) being based directly on the comparison between the observed D_t and sampled D'_t photon-click trajectories. Unfortunately, Eq. (7) would then require a temporal distance measure [82], $\delta(D_t, D'_t)$, applicable to point processes [79], which is known (e.g., in the case of the Wasserstein distance [83]) to be computationally demanding. Additionally, calibrating the ϵ threshold to work across the whole range of Δ considered would present a further challenge. Moreover, the library used within the ABC algorithm would then need to contain the actual trajectories D'_t , as storing summary statistics $S(D'_t)$ labeled by Δ -parameter values would no longer be sufficient.

Because of these challenges, we propose using the (truncated) *histogram of waiting times* between successive photon clicks as a summary statistic. This is known to capture photon bunching and antibunching effects [76,78] and should therefore be sufficient to discriminate detuning values within the range covering $\Delta_{n=1}$ and $\Delta_{n=2}$, as marked in Fig. 5(c). This is confirmed by Fig. 9, in which we present the so-obtained waiting-time distributions based

FIG. 9. Histograms of waiting times τ between subsequent photon clicks for detunings (a) $\Delta_{n=1}$ and (b) $\Delta_{n=2}$. In each case, the data represent the average occupancies for 2000 trajectories, each of $N = 80$ photon clicks. By focusing on the *short-time regime* in the above ($\tau \leq 8\kappa^{-1}$), we see a clear difference between the distributions: (a) an exponential decrease, modestly affected by uncorrelated single-photon ($n = 1$) emissions being dominant; versus (b) a distribution dropping steeply at low τ due to double-photon ($n = 2$) emissions being favored. The error bars mark the standard deviation of the trajectory samples used.

on considering 2000 simulated trajectories, each containing $N = 80$ photon clicks, for the two detuning values of interest: $\Delta_{n=1}$ and $\Delta_{n=2}$.

Although a histogram of waiting times does not capture the full information about a given trajectory—in particular, the ordering of the clicks is lost, so we expect it to be insufficient around $\Delta_{n=3}$ when photons are emitted in triplets—we show that it suffices for our purposes. Furthermore, we ignore the nonstationarity of the underlying optomechanical dynamics, as it occurs at negligible timescales when compared to the total durations of the trajectories considered.

Importantly, when constructing the histogram, we restrict ourselves to interclick intervals of short duration, i.e., $\tau < 8\kappa^{-1}$ in Fig. 9, as we expect the photon-bunching effects to alter the—otherwise exponential—waiting-time distribution only at short timescales. Although this approach loses information about the total emission time, which can only be inferred from the full histogram, we presume it to be (mostly) irrelevant and therefore decide not to include (again) the total time as a secondary summary statistic.

Finally, within the ABC algorithm (Algorithm 1), we employ the L2 norm within the acceptance rule (7), i.e.,

$$\delta(S(D_t), S(D'_t)) = \sqrt{\sum_i (x_i - x'_i)^2}, \quad (47)$$

FIG. 10. ABC performance for the nonlinear optomechanical system using the (truncated) histogram of waiting times as the summary statistic. In particular, the acceptance criterion of the ABC uses the L2 norm (47) between the histograms representing the waiting-time distribution in the range of short-time intervals, with each trajectory consisting of $N = 80$ photon clicks. As in Fig. 8, two different values of detuning are considered: (a)–(c) $\Delta = \Delta_{n=1} \approx -2.8\kappa$ and (d)–(f) $\Delta = \Delta_{n=2} \approx -5.6\kappa$, with each subplot (a)–(f) being computed for a different photon-click trajectory. Importantly, in all the cases, the ABC algorithm is now capable of reproducing the true posterior (black), while a less stringent ϵ threshold (different colors) must now be chosen due to much larger numbers of samples, ν , being required for the method to converge. The library of trajectories used is the same as the previous implementation of ABC in Fig. 8 and can be found in Ref. [81].

where $S(D_t)$ is the (truncated) time-binned histogram of the interclick waiting times, as in Fig. 9, and x_i represents the respective sizes of histogram entries.

4. Results

In Fig. 10, we present the resulting ABC-based posterior distributions, which should be compared directly against the previous ones of Fig. 8, with the same photon-click trajectories being considered. Crucially, the ABC algorithm is now capable of reproducing the true posterior in both the $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ regimes. For the $n = 1$ regime, we see in Figs. 10(a)–10(c) better performance of than in Figs. 8(a)–8(c), as the values of Δ around $n = 3$ are now excluded within the posterior; however, the distribution itself is no longer as smooth. This is a consequence of the discretization induced by the finite width

of bins used to construct the histogram and the low number of clicks ($N = 80$) composing single trajectories, for which the L2 norm (47) is evaluated. Still, despite similar discontinuities, we observe a significant improvement for $n = 2$ in Figs. 10(a)–10(f). As we tighten the ϵ thresholds in Fig. 10, we observe that sometimes none of the samples is accepted, indicating that these would require a much higher number of samples than the $\nu = 4 \times 10^5$ used here. Nevertheless, for looser thresholds, we manage to obtain good results even with the number of samples at hand.

We also emphasize that it should be possible to further improve the ABC method with better calibration, not only of the acceptance threshold but also of the width of the time bins used to construct the histograms in Fig. 9. In principle, such a calibration offers more flexibility than when comparing only the summary statistics; however, even with the minimal calibration performed here, we can already

see good overall performance of the ABC algorithm in Fig. 10.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have approached the problem of performing quantum Bayesian inference when the underlying quantum system does not allow for efficient computation of the likelihood function, but the simulation of measurement data still remains tractable thanks to the quantum Monte-Carlo techniques [47–51]. We argue that the reconstruction of the posterior distribution is still possible by resorting to approximate sampling-based methods. In particular, by building a sufficiently large library of measurement data, we demonstrate that likelihood-free approaches—in particular, the ABC algorithm [61, 62]—can be used to reconstruct the posterior.

To show the applicability of our methods, we consider the examples of a two-level atom and an optomechanical system, both being driven by classical light and continuously probed by photodetection. The former allows us to study the trade-off between the accuracy and efficiency of the ABC algorithm, as the inference problem can be solved analytically. In stark contrast, in the latter case, the sampling-based method is often essential to obtain results within a reasonable computation time. Yet, understanding the quantum statistics exhibited by the emitted photons [76] (bunching and antibunching) then becomes crucial to choosing appropriate statistical tests within the ABC algorithm, allowing it to effectively distinguish between different datasets.

In each case, we explicitly demonstrate how the ABC algorithm should be tailored. In particular, we identify the summary statistic of the measured data that is sufficient to characterize the underlying process. Moreover, we study how to choose the thresholds for the acceptance criteria used in rejection sampling, which, if chosen too tight, may require impractically large numbers of samples. For the nonlinear optomechanical system, we demonstrate that the histogram of waiting times can be used as a summary statistic that is sensitive to photon-bunching effects, allowing the ABC algorithm to reconstruct the posterior distribution reasonably well despite minimal calibration; however, let us note that if one needs to reconstruct the posterior over the full parameter range—although unlikely—then ABC can only be used to infer an “intermediate” posterior that is already narrowed down to relevant parameter ranges based on the data. This narrowed posterior can then be used as a prior by more computationally demanding methods, which can be effective thanks to the restricted parameter range.

In addition to the open quantum systems considered here, we emphasize again that the methods presented may also be applicable to a wide range of physical systems.

More precisely, any system that possesses the *asymmetry* such that it is easy to simulate and sample from its measurement data but hard to compute the likelihood, will benefit from the algorithmic approach described in this work. This is the case, for instance, in Hamiltonian learning [64,65], but one may also think of other scenarios in which combining quantum Monte Carlo techniques [47–51] with other methods makes sampling easy while the likelihood computation remains hard. For example, this applies to many-body systems that can be mapped onto spin models [84], where quantum-jump dynamics can be efficiently simulated with help of matrix-product-state representations [85–87].

For the above reasons, we believe that our results pave the way for using likelihood-free inference methods across different experimental platforms. A natural next step is to verify their performance in particular quantum estimation tasks, while combining them with other statistical inference techniques such as Markov-chain Monte Carlo methods and the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm, as well as particle filters [54]. These are widely used to avoid the need to consider the full parameter space, which, in contrast to our work, can pose a serious challenge when inferring multiple (multidimensional) parameters from the measurement data. We leave this as an interesting line of research to be pursued in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Stephen Johnson, Klaus Mølmer, Mădălin Guță, and John Calsamiglia for many helpful comments. Our work was supported by the Foundation for Polish Science within the “Quantum Optical Technologies” project carried out within the International Research Agendas program, cofinanced by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund. Project C’MON-QSENS! is supported by the National Science Centre (Grant No. 2019/32/Z/ST2/00026), Poland under QuantaERA, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 731473. L.A.C. also acknowledges project CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004649 (QUEEN-TEC) from the Czech Republic’s MEYS, supported by the EU and Grant No. 21-13265X of the Czech Science Foundation. This research was also funded in whole or in part by the National Science Centre, Poland under Grant No. 2023/50/E/ST2/00457.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this article are openly available [81].

APPENDIX: DERIVATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AVERAGE WAITING TIME AND AVERAGE TOTAL TIME

In this appendix, we derive the expectation value for the total time to emit a fixed number of photons for a system that resets into a common state after emission. We begin by noting that the total time to emit N photons is the sum of the waiting times between emissions, i.e., that of Eq. (42). We can then write the expectation value of this variable as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle t_N \rangle &= \int \left(\prod_{i=1}^N d\Delta t_i w(\Delta t_i) \right) \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta t_i \\ &= N \int d\Delta t w(\Delta t) \Delta t \\ &= N \langle \Delta t \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Here, we have used the fact that $w(\Delta t_i)$ is the same after each emission. The result is as one would expect: the expected time to emit N photons is simply N multiplied by the expected waiting time for one photon.

Similarly, we may calculate the variance of the total time to emit N photons in terms of the single-photon waiting time. First, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \langle t_N^2 \rangle &= \int \left(\prod_{i=1}^N d\Delta t_i w(\Delta t_i) \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Delta t_k \right)^2 \\ &= \int \left(\prod_{i=1}^N d\Delta t_i w(\Delta t_i) \right) \sum_{k,l=1}^N \Delta t_k \Delta t_l \\ &= \int \left(\prod_{i=1}^N d\Delta t_i w(\Delta t_i) \right) \left(\sum_{k=l}^N \Delta t_k^2 + \sum_{k \neq l} \Delta t_k \Delta t_l \right) \\ &= N \langle (\Delta t)^2 \rangle + 2 \binom{N}{2} \langle \Delta t \rangle^2 \\ &= N \langle (\Delta t)^2 \rangle + N(N-1) \langle \Delta t \rangle^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

We then calculate the variance to be

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}[t_N] &= \langle t_N^2 \rangle - \langle t_N \rangle^2 \\ &= N \langle (\Delta t)^2 \rangle + N(N-1) \langle \Delta t \rangle^2 - N^2 \langle \Delta t \rangle^2 \\ &= N \langle (\Delta t)^2 \rangle - N \langle \Delta t \rangle^2 \\ &= N (\langle (\Delta t)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta t \rangle^2) \\ &= N \text{Var}[\Delta t]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

We have thus shown that the variance of the expected time to emit N photons is related to the variance of the single-photon waiting time by a factor of N .

- [1] O. E. Barndorff-Nielsen, R. D. Gill, and P. E. Jupp, On quantum statistical inference, *J. R. Stat. Soc. B* **65**, 775 (2003).
- [2] V. Giovannetti, S. Lloyd, and L. Maccone, Quantum-enhanced measurements: Beating the standard quantum limit, *Science* **306**, 1330 (2004).
- [3] M. G. A. Paris, Quantum estimation for quantum technology, *Int. J. Quantum Inf.* **07**, 125 (2009).
- [4] R. Demkowicz-Dobrzański, M. Jarzyna, and J. Kołodyński, in *Progress in Optics*, edited by E. Wolf (Elsevier, 2015), Vol. 60, pp. 345–435, arXiv:1405.7703 [quant-ph].
- [5] H. Yuan and C.-H. F. Fung, Quantum parameter estimation with general dynamics, *npj Quantum Inf.* **3**, 1 (2017).
- [6] V. Giovannetti, S. Lloyd, and L. Maccone, Quantum-enhanced positioning and clock synchronization, *Nature* **412**, 417 (2001).
- [7] V. Giovannetti, S. Lloyd, and L. Maccone, Quantum metrology, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96**, 010401 (2006).
- [8] V. Giovannetti, S. Lloyd, and L. Maccone, Advances in quantum metrology, *Nat. Photonics* **5**, 222 (2011).
- [9] L. Pezzè, A. Smerzi, M. K. Oberthaler, R. Schmied, and P. Treutlein, Quantum metrology with nonclassical states of atomic ensembles, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **90**, 035005 (2018).
- [10] D. Braun, G. Adesso, F. Benatti, R. Floreanini, U. Marzolino, M. W. Mitchell, and S. Pirandola, Quantum-enhanced measurements without entanglement, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **90**, 035006 (2018).
- [11] S. Colombo, E. Pedrozo-Peñañiel, and V. Vuletić, Entanglement-enhanced optical atomic clocks, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **121**, 210502 (2022).
- [12] D. Budker and M. Romalis, Optical magnetometry, *Nat. Phys.* **3**, 227 (2007).
- [13] A. D. Cronin, J. Schmiedmayer, and D. E. Pritchard, Optics and interferometry with atoms and molecules, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **81**, 1051 (2009).
- [14] K. Bongs, M. Holynski, J. Vovrosh, P. Bouyer, G. Condon, E. Rasel, C. Schubert, W. P. Schleich, and A. Roura, Taking atom interferometric quantum sensors from the laboratory to real-world applications, *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **1**, 731 (2019).
- [15] M. Tse, H. Yu, N. Kijbunchoo, A. Fernandez-Galiana, P. Dupej, L. Barsotti, C. D. Blair, D. D. Brown, S. E. Dwyer, A. Effler, *et al.*, Quantum-enhanced advanced LIGO detectors in the era of gravitational-wave astronomy, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **123**, 231107 (2019).
- [16] J. Veitch, V. Raymond, B. Farr, W. Farr, P. Graff, S. Vitale, B. Aylott, K. Blackburn, N. Christensen, M. Coughlin, *et al.*, Parameter estimation for compact binaries with ground-based gravitational-wave observations using the LALInference software library, *Phys. Rev. D* **91**, 042003 (2015).
- [17] B. P. Abbott, R. Abbott, T. D. Abbott, S. Abraham, F. Acernese, K. Ackley, C. Adams, V. B. Adya, C. Affeldt, M. Agathos, *et al.*, A guide to LIGO–Virgo detector noise and extraction of transient gravitational-wave signals, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **37**, 055002 (2020).
- [18] H. Yu, L. McCuller, M. Tse, N. Kijbunchoo, L. Barsotti, and N. Mavalvala, Quantum correlations between light and the kilogram-mass mirrors of LIGO, *Nature* **583**, 43 (2020).
- [19] M. Aspelmeyer, T. J. Kippenberg, and F. Marquardt, Cavity optomechanics, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **86**, 1391 (2014).

- [20] W. Wieczorek, S. G. Hofer, J. Hoelscher-Obermaier, R. Riedinger, K. Hammerer, and M. Aspelmeyer, Optimal state estimation for cavity optomechanical systems, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **114**, 223601 (2015).
- [21] M. Rossi, D. Mason, J. Chen, and A. Schliesser, Observing and verifying the quantum trajectory of a mechanical resonator, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **123**, 163601 (2019).
- [22] J. Geremia, J. K. Stockton, A. C. Doherty, and H. Mabuchi, Quantum Kalman filtering and the Heisenberg limit in atomic magnetometry, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **91**, 250801 (2003).
- [23] K. Mølmer and L. B. Madsen, Estimation of a classical parameter with Gaussian probes: Magnetometry with collective atomic spins, *Phys. Rev. A* **70**, 052102 (2004).
- [24] F. Albarelli, M. A. C. Rossi, M. G. A. Paris, and M. G. Genoni, Ultimate limits for quantum magnetometry via time-continuous measurements, *New J. Phys.* **19**, 123011 (2017).
- [25] J. Amorós-Binefa and J. Kolodyński, Noisy atomic magnetometry in real time, *New J. Phys.* **23**, 012030 (2021).
- [26] V. P. Belavkin, in *Modeling and Control of Systems*, edited by A. Blaquiére (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1989) pp. 245–265.
- [27] M. B. Plenio and P. L. Knight, The quantum-jump approach to dissipative dynamics in quantum optics, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **70**, 101 (1998).
- [28] K. Jacobs, *Quantum Measurement Theory and Its Applications* (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2014).
- [29] S. Gammelmark and K. Mølmer, Bayesian parameter inference from continuously monitored quantum systems, *Phys. Rev. A* **87**, 032115 (2013).
- [30] A. H. Kiilerich and K. Mølmer, Estimation of atomic interaction parameters by photon counting, *Phys. Rev. A* **89**, 052110 (2014).
- [31] A. H. Kiilerich and K. Mølmer, Bayesian parameter estimation by continuous homodyne detection, *Phys. Rev. A* **94**, 032103 (2016).
- [32] H. I. Nurdin and N. Yamamoto, *Linear Dynamical Quantum Systems* (Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 2017).
- [33] R. Hamerly and H. Mabuchi, Advantages of coherent feedback for cooling quantum oscillators, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 173602 (2012).
- [34] N. Yamamoto, Coherent versus measurement feedback: Linear systems theory for quantum information, *Phys. Rev. X* **4**, 041029 (2014).
- [35] D. J. Wilson, V. Sudhir, N. Piro, R. Schilling, A. Ghadimi, and T. J. Kippenberg, Measurement-based control of a mechanical oscillator at its thermal decoherence rate, *Nature* **524**, 325 (2015).
- [36] M. Rossi, D. Mason, J. Chen, Y. Tsaturyan, and A. Schliesser, Measurement-based quantum control of mechanical motion, *Nature* **563**, 53 (2018).
- [37] V. Sudhir, D. J. Wilson, R. Schilling, H. Schütz, S. A. Fedorov, A. H. Ghadimi, A. Nunnenkamp, and T. J. Kippenberg, Appearance and disappearance of quantum correlations in measurement-based feedback control of a mechanical oscillator, *Phys. Rev. X* **7**, 011001 (2017).
- [38] M. Ernzer, M. Bosch Aguilera, M. Brunelli, G.-L. Schmid, T. M. Karg, C. Bruder, P. P. Potts, and P. Treutlein, Optical coherent feedback control of a mechanical oscillator, *Phys. Rev. X* **13**, 021023 (2023).
- [39] A. Setter, M. Toroš, J. F. Ralph, and H. Ulbricht, Real-time Kalman filter: Cooling of an optically levitated nanoparticle, *Phys. Rev. A* **97**, 033822 (2018).
- [40] L. Magrini, P. Rosenzweig, C. Bach, A. Deutschmann-Olek, S. G. Hofer, S. Hong, N. Kiesel, A. Kugi, and M. Aspelmeyer, Real-time optimal quantum control of mechanical motion at room temperature, *Nature* **595**, 373 (2021).
- [41] M. Tsang, J. H. Shapiro, and S. Lloyd, Quantum theory of optical temporal phase and instantaneous frequency. II. Continuous-time limit and state-variable approach to phase-locked loop design, *Phys. Rev. A* **79**, 053843 (2009).
- [42] R. Jiménez-Martínez, J. Kolodyński, C. Troullinou, V. G. Lucivero, J. Kong, and M. W. Mitchell, Signal tracking beyond the time resolution of an atomic sensor by Kalman filtering, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120**, 040503 (2018).
- [43] J. D. Cohen, S. M. Meenehan, G. S. MacCabe, S. Gröblacher, A. H. Safavi-Naeini, F. Marsili, M. D. Shaw, and O. Painter, Phonon counting and intensity interferometry of a nanomechanical resonator, *Nature* **520**, 522 (2015).
- [44] R. Riedinger, A. Wallucks, I. Marinković, C. Löschnauer, M. Aspelmeyer, S. Hong, and S. Gröblacher, Remote quantum entanglement between two micromechanical oscillators, *Nature* **556**, 473 (2018).
- [45] I. Galinskiy, Y. Tsaturyan, Y. Tsaturyan, M. Parniak, and E. S. Polzik, Phonon counting thermometry of an ultracoherent membrane resonator near its motional ground state, *Optica* **7**, 718 (2020).
- [46] N. Fiaschi, B. Hensen, A. Wallucks, R. Benevides, J. Li, T. P. M. Alegre, and S. Gröblacher, Optomechanical quantum teleportation, *Nat. Photonics* **15**, 817 (2021).
- [47] J. Dalibard, Y. Castin, and K. Mølmer, Wave-function approach to dissipative processes in quantum optics, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **68**, 580 (1992).
- [48] H. Carmichael, *An Open Systems Approach to Quantum Optics* (Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 1993).
- [49] G. C. Hegerfeldt, How to reset an atom after a photon detection: Applications to photon-counting processes, *Phys. Rev. A* **47**, 449 (1993).
- [50] K. Mølmer, Y. Castin, and J. Dalibard, Monte Carlo wavefunction method in quantum optics, *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **10**, 524 (1993).
- [51] K. Mølmer and Y. Castin, Monte Carlo wavefunctions in quantum optics, *Quantum Semiclass. Opt.* **8**, 49 (1996).
- [52] H. L. van Trees, *Detection, Estimation and Modulation Theory* (Wiley, New York, NY USA, 1968), Vol. I.
- [53] S. M. Kay, *Fundamentals of Statistical Signal Processing: Estimation Theory* (Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ USA, 1993).
- [54] K. P. Murphy, *Machine Learning: A Probabilistic Perspective* (MIT Press, Cambridge, MA USA, 2012).
- [55] C. Granade, C. Ferrie, I. Hincks, S. Casagrande, T. Alexander, J. Gross, M. Kononenko, and Y. Sanders, QInfer: Statistical inference software for quantum applications, *Quantum* **1**, 5 (2017).
- [56] W. R. Gilks, S. Richardson, and D. J. Spiegelhalter (Eds.), *Markov Chain Monte Carlo in Practice* (CRC Press, New York, NY USA, 1995).

- [57] A. Aeppli, K. Kim, W. Warfield, M. S. Safronova, and J. Ye, Clock with 8×10^{-19} systematic uncertainty, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **133**, 023401 (2024).
- [58] J. I. Cirac, D. Pérez-García, N. Schuch, and F. Verstraete, Matrix product states and projected entangled pair states: Concepts, symmetries, theorems, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **93**, 045003 (2021).
- [59] A. Godley and M. Guta, Adaptive measurement filter: Efficient strategy for optimal estimation of quantum Markov chains, *Quantum* **7**, 973 (2023).
- [60] M. A. Beaumont, W. Zhang, and D. J. Balding, Approximate Bayesian computation in population genetics, *Genetics* **162**, 2025 (2002).
- [61] B. M. Turner and T. Van Zandt, A tutorial on approximate Bayesian computation, *J. Math. Psychol.* **56**, 69 (2012).
- [62] S. Sisson, Y. Fan, and M. Beaumont, *Handbook of Approximate Bayesian Computation*, Chapman & Hall/CRC Handbooks of Modern Statistical Methods (CRC Press, 2018).
- [63] C. Catana, T. Kypraios, and M. Guță, Maximum likelihood versus likelihood-free quantum system identification in the atom maser, *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.* **47**, 415302 (2014).
- [64] N. Wiebe, C. Granade, C. Ferrie, and D. G. Cory, Hamiltonian learning and certification using quantum resources, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112**, 190501 (2014).
- [65] N. Wiebe, C. Granade, C. Ferrie, and D. Cory, Quantum Hamiltonian learning using imperfect quantum resources, *Phys. Rev. A* **89**, 042314 (2014).
- [66] C. Drovandi and D. T. Frazier, A comparison of likelihood-free methods with and without summary statistics, *Stat. Comput.* **32**, 42 (2022).
- [67] V. Cimini, E. Polino, M. Valeri, I. Gianani, N. Spagnolo, G. Corrielli, A. Crespi, R. Osellame, M. Barbieri, and F. Sciarrino, Calibration of multiparameter sensors via machine learning at the single-photon level, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **15**, 044003 (2021).
- [68] M. Khanahmadi and K. Mølmer, Time-dependent atomic magnetometry with a recurrent neural network, *Phys. Rev. A* **103**, 032406 (2021).
- [69] S. P. Nolan, L. Pezzè, and A. Smerzi, Frequentist parameter estimation with supervised learning, *AVS Quantum Sci.* **3**, 034401 (2021).
- [70] H.-Y. Hsieh, J. Ning, Y.-R. Chen, H.-C. Wu, H. L. Chen, C.-M. Wu, and R.-K. Lee, Direct parameter estimations from machine learning-enhanced quantum state tomography, *Symmetry* **14**, 874 (2022).
- [71] R. Porotti, A. Essig, B. Huard, and F. Marquardt, Deep reinforcement learning for quantum state preparation with weak nonlinear measurements, *Quantum* **6**, 747 (2022).
- [72] E. Rinaldi, M. G. Lastre, S. G. Herrerros, S. Ahmed, M. Khanahmadi, F. Nori, and C. S. Muñoz, Parameter estimation from quantum-jump data using neural networks, *Quantum Sci. Technol.* **9**, 035018 (2024).
- [73] M. A. Beaumont, Approximate Bayesian computation in evolution and ecology, *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* **41**, 379 (2010).
- [74] H.-P. Breuer and F. Petruccione, *The Theory of Open Quantum Systems* (Oxford University Press, New York, NY USA, 2002).
- [75] G. Grimmett and D. Stirzaker, *Probability and Random Processes* (Oxford University Press, New York, NY USA, 2001), 3rd ed.
- [76] L. A. Clark, B. Markowicz, and J. Kołodyński, Exploiting non-linear effects in optomechanical sensors with continuous photon-counting, *Quantum* **6**, 812 (2022).
- [77] Y.-C. Liu, Y.-F. Xiao, X. Luan, and C. W. Wong, Dynamic dissipative cooling of a mechanical resonator in strong coupling optomechanics, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **110**, 153606 (2013).
- [78] A. Kronwald, M. Ludwig, and F. Marquardt, Full photon statistics of a light beam transmitted through an optomechanical system, *Phys. Rev. A* **87**, 013847 (2013).
- [79] B. Everitt and A. Skrondal, *The Cambridge Dictionary of Statistics* (Cambridge University Press, New York, NY USA, 2010).
- [80] X. Didelot, R. G. Everitt, A. M. Johansen, and D. J. Lawson, Likelihood-free estimation of model evidence, *Bayesian Anal.* **6**, 49 (2011).
- [81] L. A. Clark and J. Kołodyński, *Efficient inference of quantum system parameters by approximate Bayesian computation – ABC libraries* (Dane Badawcze UW, 2025).
- [82] H. Su, S. Liu, B. Zheng, X. Zhou, and K. Zheng, A survey of trajectory distance measures and performance evaluation, *VLDB J.* **29**, 3 (2020).
- [83] S. Xiao, M. Farajtabar, X. Ye, J. Yan, L. Song, and H. Zha, in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Curran Associates, Inc., 2017), Vol. 30.
- [84] M. T. Manzoni, D. E. Chang, and J. S. Douglas, Simulating quantum light propagation through atomic ensembles using matrix product states, *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 1743 (2017).
- [85] I. Lesanovsky, M. van Horssen, M. Guță, and J. P. Garrahan, Characterization of dynamical phase transitions in quantum jump trajectories beyond the properties of the stationary state, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **110**, 150401 (2013).
- [86] A. J. Daley, Quantum trajectories and open many-body quantum systems, *Adv. Phys.* **63**, 77 (2014).
- [87] M. L. Wall, A. Safavi-Naini, and A. M. Rey, Simulating generic spin-boson models with matrix product states, *Phys. Rev. A* **94**, 053637 (2016).